

Table S3: Variability in the sediment load, discharge and the estimated charcoal abundance across the hydrological station in the YSB.

Distance (km)	Sediment load (Million tons/year)#	Average annual discharge(m³/s)#	Charcoal count/tons of sediments*
313	0.70	136	7.0×10 ¹³
423	4.04	94	8.9×10 ¹⁴
500	0.70	77	6.7×10 ¹³
646	0.87	89	4.7×10 ¹⁴
964	2.09	106	3.9×10 ¹⁴
1079	13.22	679	3.0×10 ¹⁴
1172	41.91	1382	1.7×10 ¹⁴

Bawa et al.(2014)

*Charcoal count per tons of sediment= $(CC \times SL \times 10^6) / \rho$

CC: Charcoal count/ml; SL: Sediment load; ρ : bulk density of sediments